

Evaluating the Impact of Decreasing Efficiency on the Determination of Measured Total Multiplication

George E. McKenzie^{1,*}, Jawad R. Moussa¹, Jesson D. Hutchinson¹

¹Los Alamos National Laboratory, PO BOX 1663, Los Alamos, NM, USA

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ABSTRACT

When performing multiplication measurements, it is often desirable to know how the derived multiplication relates to the detection efficiency. This is increasingly important as many low efficiency detectors are being investigated to measure multiplication in a variety of contexts (e.g. safeguards, criticality safety). Much of this research is related to the cost and availability of He-3 which has been the standard for the past 80 years. This work investigates the ability to determine the multiplication of a well-known system using the NoMAD detector. The multiplying system consists of approximately 43 kg of HEU in a spherical shape which has a multiplication just above 10. The NoMAD detector consists of 15 He-3 tubes embedded inside a polyethylene matrix. The approach applied in this work utilizes the Hage-Cifarelli formalism of the Feynman Variance-to-Mean method to determine multiplication from the measurements. To examine the impact of efficiency, the data was post processed to systematically remove detectors until only one tube remained. The result of this analysis showed that the multiplication can still be accurately determined using detectors with an efficiency much less than 0.2%.

Keywords: Neutron Noise, Feynman Variance-to-Mean, Efficiency, He-3, Multiplication

1. INTRODUCTION

Measurements of neutron multiplication are essential to many fields of study including: criticality safety, reactor kinetics, and nuclear safeguards. An increasingly common study in these fields revolves around the use of new detector technologies [1, 2, 3] for the determination of neutron multiplication. This push for new technology is typically motivated by the low availability and rising cost associated with He-3 which is currently considered the gold standard for neutron detection systems. New technologies are also of interest in supporting other neutron kinetics techniques which require much faster timing. However, questions pertaining to the loss of overall detection efficiency are commonly posed when exploring the development of new technologies. As such, this work evaluates the impact of decreasing detection efficiency on the effective determination of sample multiplication.

The measurements in this work were performed on the fifth configuration of the Measurements of Uranium Subcritical and Critical (MUSiC) experiment [4]. The MUSiC experiment consists of ten different configurations spanning a drastic range in criticality from deeply subcritical to supercritical. The experiment consisted of nesting highly enriched uranium (HEU) hemishells, often referred to as the Rocky Flats shells, that are approximately 0.3175 cm thick (0.125 in). The configurations are adjusted by changing the total HEU mass by adding hemishells. For all of the configurations, data was taken on several different detection systems including a He-3 multiplicity detector named the NoMAD [5], an EJ-309 organic scintillator system named RAM-RODD [6], four bare, high pressure He-3 tubes, and a trans-stilbene organic scintillator system named OSCAR [1].

The fifth configuration of the MUSiC critical experiment was a subcritical configuration consisting of shells 3-40, and weighs approximately 43 kg. A photo of the configuration is shown in Fig. 1. Based on

Figure 1. Photo of configuration 5 of the MUSiC experiment.

preliminary simulations (the configuration is currently being extensively benchmarked [7]), the system should have a total multiplication of approximately 11.

The data examined in this work focuses on the measured NoMAD data. The NoMAD detection system, shown in 2, is a He-3 based multiplicity counter that consists of 15 He-3 tubes pressurized to 10 atm, and embedded in a polyethylene matrix to increase detection efficiency [5]. All of the 15 tubes are connected to a single time stream, so the list-mode [8] data collected from the tubes is recorded on a single time stream.

2. METHOD

The method used to determine detection efficiency in this work is the Hage-Cifarelli formalism of the Feynman Variance-to-Mean method. A surface level description of the method is given in Section 2, for more details refer to the original papers [9, 10, 11].

2.1. Feynman Variance-to-Mean

The Feynman Variance-to-Mean method infers neutron multiplication based on analysis of the temporal distribution of counts from a detector. This method was developed by Richard Feynman in 1944 to analyze early criticality experiments at Los Alamos [10, 11]. The method consists of development of a Feynman histogram. These histograms are developed by taking a time stream of neutron detections, dividing it up into equal sized time gates, and then counting the number of neutrons in each gate. This data is built into a histogram, for that time gate, and compared to a Poisson distribution with the same mean. An example of a Feynman histogram is shown in Fig. 3. The Poisson distribution is selected because a randomly distributed source would follow a Poisson distribution, meaning that any “excess” variance is related to the system multiplication. The “excess” variance was heuristically derived by

Figure 2. Photo of the NoMAD detector.

Feynman and is shown in Eq. 1. The mean, variance, and dispersion of this distribution are recorded, and the entire process is repeated for another time gate.

$$Y = \frac{\bar{c}^2 - \bar{c}^2}{\bar{c}} - 1 = \frac{\epsilon (\bar{v}^2 - \bar{v})}{\bar{v}^2 v_p^2} \left(1 - \frac{(1 - e^{-\alpha t})}{\alpha t} \right) \quad (1)$$

After repeating for many gate widths, the mean, variance, and dispersion are plotted as a function of gate width. This distribution is fit to determine the singles, doubles, and triples rates which are fundamentally the likelihood of measuring one, two, or three counts in a given period of time.

2.2. Hage-Cifarelli Formalism

The Hage-Cifarelli formalism uses the first three moments of the neutron counting distribution to determine 2-3 unknowns from the set of equations created by the moments [9, 12]. The formalism is used in this work to determine the spontaneous fission rate (F_S) (which is proportionate to fissile mass) and leakage multiplication (M_L). We assume the detector efficiency (ϵ) and the (α, n) source is known to constrain the equations. Because the system is known to have negligible amounts of (α, n) neutrons, the singles and doubles count rates simplify to Eqs. 2 and 3, respectively [12].

$$R_1 = \epsilon M_L \bar{v}_{s1} F_S \quad (2)$$

$$R_2 = \epsilon^2 M_L^2 F_S \left(\bar{v}_{s2} + \frac{M_L - 1}{\bar{v}_{l1} - 1} \bar{v}_{s1} \bar{v}_{l2} \right) \quad (3)$$

Figure 3. A Feynman histogram example from MUSiC configuration 5.

Eqs. 2 and 3 can be rearranged to solve for the mass of the spontaneous fissioner, and the leakage multiplication which are shown in Eqs. 4 and 5, respectively. Some mathematical steps have been left out for brevity, the full derivation was supplied by Hutchinson et. al. [12].

$$F_S = \frac{R_1}{\epsilon M_L \bar{v}_{S1}} \quad (4)$$

$$a_1 = \frac{\bar{v}_{S1} \bar{v}_{I2}}{\bar{v}_{I1} - 1}$$

$$a_2 = \bar{v}_{S2} - a_1$$

$$a_3 = -\frac{R_2 \bar{v}_{S1}}{R_1 \epsilon}$$

$$M_L = \frac{-a_2 + \sqrt{a_2^2 - 4a_1 a_3}}{2a_1} \quad (5)$$

The leakage multiplication refers to the multiplication seen outside the system for each source neutron introduced into the system. For easier comparison to simulation, the leakage multiplication needs to be converted to total multiplication. This can be derived from the Eqs. 6 and 7 developed by Serber [13].

$$M_L = 1 + Q_f (\bar{v} - 1 - \alpha_{CR}) \quad (6)$$

$$M_T = 1 + Q_f \bar{v} \quad (7)$$

$$M_L = 1 + \frac{M_T - 1}{\bar{v}} (\bar{v} - 1 - \alpha_{CR}) \quad (8)$$

$$M_T = \frac{\bar{\nu}M_L - 1 - \alpha_{CR}}{\bar{\nu} - 1 - \alpha_{CR}} \quad (9)$$

3. ANALYSIS

To obtain the multiplication from each of the data files, an analysis program called Momentum was used [14]. This program leverages the methodology from Section 2 to derive the multiplication. The multiplication is determined assuming the efficiency is known and the ratio of (α, n) starters is negligible. Lower efficiency configurations are generated by the removal of tubes in the NoMAD beginning in the back. For reference, the layout of the tubes in the NoMAD is shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. Layout of the tube distribution in the NoMAD.

3.1. Detector Efficiency

The detector efficiency for each tube was determined experimentally. The exact setup used of the experiment was used to measure only the Cf-252 source. The emission of the source was well-known, and decayed to the exact day of the measurement. The count rate in each tube divided by the overall source emission rate gives the efficiency of each tube in the detector. The detector efficiency of the tubes in a selected configuration are added together and included in Table I.

3.2. Multiplication

Using Momentum version 0.45.10b, the total multiplication in Table I were derived from the MUSiC configuration 5 data.

The data in Table I is plotted as a function of efficiency. Typically, a 1%-2% uncertainty is expected on multiplication measurements. So a 1% line is put on each side of the assumed baseline multiplication in Fig. 5.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The goal of this work was to examine the effect of decreasing efficiency on the resulting multiplication. This result can have impacts for a variety of different applications, but is especially important as new detection systems are examined for neutron noise measurements. Based on the results presented in Section 3, it may be inferred that efficiencies below 0.2% may produce non-conservative (lower than

Table I. Derived Multiplication from Each Configuration.

Configuration	ϵ	M_T
Full NoMAD	0.012092	11.15 ± 0.02
Remove Tube 14 and 15	0.010701	11.19 ± 0.03
Remove Tube 8, 13, 14 and 15	0.008743	\pm
Remove Tube 8, 9, 12, 13, 14 and 15	0.006686	11.23 ± 0.03
Remove Rows 2 and 3	0.004520	\pm
Remove Tube 1 and 7 and Rows 2 and 3	0.003349	11.27 ± 0.05
Only Tube 3, 4 and 5	0.002054	11.10 ± 0.03
Only Tube 4	0.000691	10.53 ± 0.06

Figure 5. Multiplication as a function of efficiency.

actual) multiplication results.

Unfortunately, there is only a single point below this threshold, and this work only examines a single case of a fast HEU system. Future work would examine, even lower efficiencies on the MUSiC configuration 5 to further highlight the trend hypothesized in this work. This would likely need to be performed using simulations. Other future work would examine different spectra, multiplication levels, and possibly even different special nuclear materials.

NOMENCLATURE

- α prompt neutron decay constant
- α_{CR} ratio of capture cross section to fission cross section
- $\bar{\nu}^2$ variance of the number of neutrons produced, per fission
- $\bar{\nu}_{I1}$ mean number of neutrons emitted by the primary induced fissioner

$\bar{\nu}_{I2}$	mean number of neutrons emitted by the secondary induced fissioner
$\bar{\nu}_{S1}$	mean number of neutrons emitted by the primary spontaneous fissioner
$\bar{\nu}_{S2}$	mean number of neutrons emitted by the secondary spontaneous fissioner
$\bar{\nu}$	mean number of neutrons produced, per fission
\bar{c}^2	variance of the counts
\bar{c}	mean counts
ϵ	efficiency of detecting a neutron, per fission
ν_p	mean number of prompt neutrons produced, per fission
F_S	spontaneous fission rate isotope
M_L	leakage multiplication
M_T	total multiplication
Q_f	number of fissions that result from adding one neutron
R_1	singles count rate
R_2	doubles count rate
Y	excess variance

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